

Typology of Data Uses

An output of the FORCE11 Data Usage
Typologies Working Group

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Executive Summary

Data is being created, shared, and used at an ever increasing pace. The importance of data use is reflected in the need to describe data use types in a comprehensive and consistent way. The FORCE11 Data Usage Typologies Working Group has developed a typology which allows to describe the key dimensions of data use. The typology is agnostic with regard to data creators, users, and purposes. Thus, it is generic in principle, but due to the group's composition it is most immediately applicable to research-related use cases. It covers not only cases typically considered "reuse", but any instance of "use". The typology is comprised of three overarching dimensions, namely Access, User, and Application. Within these dimensions, a set of overall 13 categories is offered to describe data uses, with a defined set of value options for each category. When applying the typology, it is suggested to code properties of a single user, while allowing for different applications within one instance of use. The typology is envisioned by the group to be applied e.g. by repositories, funders, or meta-researchers interested in analysing how a corpus of datasets is being used. This could then be used to derive infrastructural or policy decisions. The group plans to develop metadata recommendations based on the typology, which will dock to existing schemas wherever possible.

Access

How is use enabled?

- Actor
- Data Discovery
- Point of Access
- Data Interaction
- Restriction on Use

User

Who is using the data?

- Role
- Permission
- Geography
- Discipline

Application

How are the datasets used?

- Purpose
- Activity Type
- Time of Use
- Output

Why we need a typology of data uses

The ways in which data are used are diverse, spanning many processes and communities. In an academic context, this might include re-analysis or synthesis of existing data, development and testing of software and protocols, or the creation and refinement of machine-learning algorithms. These and many other activities extend far beyond the academic sphere, for example, in family genealogical research, comparing the outcomes of different public policy proposals, or planning new city infrastructure.

Understanding the extent to which a given dataset is used for these or any other activities is a crucial need for many stakeholder groups. These include data generators, infrastructure providers, policy makers, funding organizations, as well as current and future data users. A scientist might use this information to determine untouched or underexamined areas of their field, or to demonstrate the downstream impact of their data in grant applications, progress reports, or evaluations. A team working on an online repository might use this information to plan new features, integrations, or access points. A funder might use this information to support research forecasting and inform future funding calls, and so on.

In order for this information to be made actionable, we need a typology that recognizes data usage as a discrete entity and provides uniform structure for describing that usage. Importantly, the typology should reflect a community-recognized approach that can be adopted and applied by different actors interested in collecting or utilizing data-usage information, from meta-researchers to repositories, funders and others. Only with such a typology can one sustainably monitor usage over time, compare usage across contexts and domains, and properly assign credit to those responsible for producing and providing data. As of this writing, there exist no generalizable typologies for achieving this goal. Filling this gap was the goal of our Working Group.

The work of this group aims to complement that in other areas of open data such as infrastructure or usage indicators (e.g. views, downloads or citations). Its outcome will be useful for initiatives such as the [RDA Uptake of Digital Research Infrastructure Interest Group](#), which aims to understand uptake - by whom, how and for what purposes such infrastructure is used and why it may not be used - as key for understanding user needs, barriers and opportunities.

In addition to developing a framework for possible uses, adding well-defined structure to the descriptions of data usage vastly enhances the machine actionability of that information. This is especially important as more automated means for collecting and generating usage information become available. Existing infrastructure like [DataCite](#) and [Crossref](#), for example, could harness more structured descriptions of usage to greatly enrich the context around pre-existing connections between datasets and users. Machine-learning models could ingest the schema so as to become more proficient at usage-adjacent entity extraction over large text corpora like [PubMed Central](#) or the [UK CORE](#). A data usage typology would substantially contribute to the FAIRness (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) of any collected usage information.

Overview of the Working Group

Meta-researchers; librarians;
institutional representatives;
funders; infrastructure providers

The [Working Group](#) brought together representatives with diverse expertise across the data ecosystem, including meta-researchers, funders, institutional representatives, infrastructure providers, and librarians. We aimed for broad representation of expertise and experience in data and evaluation, while acknowledging that the Working Group is predominantly composed of members from research and research-supporting organizations. The group is mostly composed of stakeholders from Europe and North America, while other regions, and in particular developing countries, are not broadly represented.

The Working Group was set up with two main goals: 1) create a community-developed typology of data uses, along with description and characteristics that identify each use type, and 2) recommend how to capture data use types in metadata. During 2025, the Working Group focused on its first goal, and the typology of data uses is the focus of this report. In the next stage, the Working Group will work on metadata recommendations, drawing on the typology described here.

Scope of the Data Usage Typology

The Working Group started its work by defining the scope of the typology. This benefited from the group's participants and the diverse perspectives they brought about data usage. As initial steps we started with foundational questions such as how to define "data" and "usage" and determining the scope of and use cases for the typology. We developed a scope articulation and iterated on it, approaching questions such as whether certain uses as e.g. data curation, would "count" as a type of data use, or whether the use of the metadata for the dataset would be considered usage.

The group settled on a scope for the typology that would cover all purposes of data use and all types of data. The typology thus includes uses of datasets created through research as well as non-research activities, such as government datasets or those generated by citizens. Similarly, we took a broad approach to considering uses, including those that happen in research but also in other activities, such as the use of data to inform policy development, in educational materials, or by the public. While our goal was to encompass a broad range of uses of data, we acknowledge that some discussions in the group may have been guided by the preponderance of actors from research, and that actors outside of academic research may have feedback about the applicability of the typology to their use cases.

Given that the focus is on datasets, other types of outputs (e.g. methods, models, or software) are not covered in the typology. The Working Group also determined that the following fall beyond the scope of the typology:

- A description of the properties (e.g. size, format, or quality) of the data, as this information is intrinsic to the dataset but not a descriptor of the use made of the data.
- Interactions that do not involve the dataset content or its metadata - processes like data storage or backup are not in scope.

Review and curation of data are in scope of the typology. They are not ends in themselves, but for reasons of consistency and because these practices are of interest to some stakeholders, we decided to include them.

The Data Usage Typology

The Working Group was convened in January 2025. The typology was developed collaboratively via contributions in monthly group meetings and asynchronous review and refinement. The Working Group distilled the Data Usage Typology into three core dimensions of use:

1. Access - How is use enabled?
2. User - Who is using the data?
3. Application - How are datasets used?

Each dimension consists of categories that provide further granularity for description of data usage. Each category has a definition and associated values, which the category can take. Values are either derived from controlled vocabularies (e.g. for countries, research disciplines and outputs) or have been newly collated, with corresponding definitions of these values. This allows to designate consistent descriptions of the manifestations associated with the category.

Access dimension

The Access dimension defines access as the permission and ability to retrieve, modify, copy, and/or move data. Within the Access dimension there are five categories: *Actor*, *Data Discovery*, *Point of Access*, *Data Interaction*, *Restriction on Use*.

The Access dimension allows the description of data usage from *data discovery* (including the mechanism used for discovery) through the *point of access* (where the user sourced the data) through *data interaction* (how the user interacted with the data, and, where applicable, transferred the data to a different location for the purposes of use), and keeps track of the possible *restriction(s) on use*. The Data Usage Typology allows the user to accurately describe the data-access workflow that is a prerequisite for data use.

Access/How is use enabled?:

Definition of "Access": The permission and ability to retrieve, modify, copy, and/or move data.

CATEGORY	DEFINITION	VALUES
Access: Actor	Type of entity which accesses data. Which type of entity accesses the data?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Human- Machine
Access: Data discovery	Infrastructure, technology or protocol used to establish the existence and location of data How is the data discovered? More than one option can be chosen.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Search Engine- Text-based publication- Catalog- Direct link- Identifier- Related links or identifiers- OAI-PMH- FAIR signposting- Personal communication- Other
Access: Point of Access	Provider, medium or source from which data were drawn for the instance of use Where does the data live?	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Data Repository- Journal- Cloud storage- Webpage- Local medium- Other
Access: Data interaction	Technical pathway or platform through which data is transferred or interacted with for the purpose of use. Which way is the data transferred or interacted with? More than one option can be chosen.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Web download- Direct download- Email- File-hosting service- Distributed Data Storage- Secure Data Enclave- API- Manual transcription- Other
Access: Restriction on use	Applicable type(s) of non-technical (e.g. ethical, legal) restrictions on use Which non-technical restrictions apply to use? More than one option can be chosen.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- License type- Local context- Data use agreement- Ethical restrictions- Committee clearance- None- Other

User dimension

The User Dimension describes the entity (human or machine) which interacts with the data. Within the User dimension there are four Categories: *Role*, *Permission*, *Geography*, *Discipline*.

The User dimension allows the description of the user's role in the context of the use of the data - *data creator, curator, consumer, reviewer* - which might have different permissions to interact with the data. One important consideration was to have a mechanism to collect information on whether the use of data was by the creators of the data or by others, as such considerations can be relevant to some stakeholders, in relation to data reach and impact for example. The *Role* category provides a means to collect this type of information. The *Geography* and *Discipline* categories aim to capture the breadth of geographical locations and academic disciplines associated with use of specific datasets, which can be important properties for repositories, institutions and funders. For the purposes of this typology, *Discipline* is described here as the user's field of research. We recognize that this is only relevant in the context of academic uses of data, but decided to include this information, as it is highly relevant for many research-related use cases of the contributing experts and to identify crossdisciplinary usage. We operationalize this category as the discipline(s) associated with the user, but we recognize that a user in one discipline may make use of data from another discipline or disciplines as those to which the users assign themselves.

User/Who is using the data?		
Definition of "User": An entity (human or machine) which interacts with the data. <small>[see relational definition of data]</small>		
CATEGORY	DEFINITION	VALUES
User: Role	Function assumed by the user with respect to the data. <i>In which role(s) does the user engage with the data?</i>	- Creator - Consumer - Curator - Reviewer
User: Permission	The type of authorization the user has with regard to interacting with the data. Which level of authorization does the user have?	- Administrator - Editor - Viewer with download - Viewer without download - None
User: Geography	The user's geographic location Where is the user located?	- Country
User: Discipline	The user's field of research What is/are the user's field(s) of research, if applicable? More than one option can be chosen.	- OECD Fields of Science and Technology vocabulary - N/A

Application dimension

The Application dimension describes the way in which the data were used. Within this Dimension there are four Categories: *Purpose, Activity type, Time of use, Output*.

The Application dimension is the heart of the Data Usage Typology - this dimension describes the user's *purpose* (examples include *Research, Tool Development, Education, Policy, Citizen Science*) and answers the question "why is the user interacting with the data?". The *Activity Type* category allows the user to select terms to describe how they used the data - such as *Model development/training, meta-analysis, exploration, validation* etc - as part of their activities. The *Time of Use* aims to capture the point in time at which the use took place - this gathers important information for tracking the usage over time. This category includes two values: *Use start time* and *use end time*, which can be used together or independently. The goal is to provide flexibility in the collection of temporal information, and include situations where data use can be asserted - e.g. a dataset is cited in a preprint - but it is not possible to determine the time point at which such use started. *Output* describes the work product that resulted from the user application - a *dissertation, educational material, journal article, policy document, standard*, and so forth. Taken together, this dimension allows tracking how and when the data was used, and connections to products associated with the use of the data, providing contextual depth to the information related to instances of data use.

Application/How are the datasets used?

Definition of "Application": Way in which the data is put to a desired use.

CATEGORY	DEFINITION	VALUES
Application: Purpose	<p>The scholarly, public, or private sector(s) or sphere(s) that characterize the activities including an instance of use.</p> <p>Why is the user interacting with the data?</p> <p>More than one option can be chosen.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Education - Reporting - Software or tool development - Commercial product - Policy - Research - Operational analytics - Citizen science - Personal/recreational - Journalism - Review - Curation - Other
Application: Activity type	<p>The specific actions, be them analytical, exploratory, or otherwise, leveraging data that constitute an instance of use.</p> <p>How is the user leveraging or interacting with the data?</p> <p>More than one option can be chosen.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Model Development/ Training - Meta-analysis - Statistical methods - Comparison or control - Benchmarking - Exploration - Validation - Reproduction/ re-analysis - Curation/cleaning - Annotation/labeling - Review - Infrastructure - Data assimilation - Other
Application: Time of use	<p>Time point at which an activity related to the data occurred.</p> <p>When does the data use occur?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use start time - Use end time
Application: Output	<p>A product resulting from an instance of use.</p> <p>What is produced from a given instance of use, if applicable?</p> <p>More than one option can be chosen.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Controlled vocabulary

Additional considerations about the breadth and structure of the typology

All of the categories provide controlled vocabularies to enable consistent input of the information, the only exception to this is the *Application: Time of use* category where the input field requires a time indicator. Where possible, we have referred to existing vocabularies or taxonomies, for example, ISO 3166 country codes for *Geography* values and the OECD Fields of Science and Technology (FoS) vocabulary for the *Discipline*.

In a number of categories, it is possible to designate more than one option among the possible Values. The motivation for this is to enable capturing as broad a range of information on use as possible. In particular, we discussed whether “one use” of data, as implemented by applying the typology once and choosing one set of values, can include more than one *Purpose*, *Activity type*, and *Output*. Ultimately, it was decided to allow multiple choice in all three categories. While restriction to single values would provide most granularity, it was decided this would create too many multiple entries and would not be manageable for many use cases.

We approached the typology with the view of capturing contextual information about the use of data, and key elements that inform understanding and insights into that use. However, we are not designating a hierarchy across the categories and also do not designate any fields as mandatory. We anticipate that in many instances of data use, it will not be possible to complete all of the categories and values in the typology, and that the capability to complete the full typology or parts of it may vary depending on the entity completing the typology - e.g. a researcher using a dataset in their research will likely be able to complete every field, while a repository that seeks to apply the typology to collect more granular information on data use may only be able to technically implement parts of it. We will pursue further conversations regarding opportunities for larger scale and machine-oriented implementation of the typology as part of the future work on metadata recommendations.

Questions and items raised during the Working Group's discussions

The typology is designed to capture data usage very broadly and at the same time, be specific enough to be unambiguous as well as practical for use cases within scope. As part of the discussion leading to the identification and selection of categories and values, the group reviewed additional elements that were ultimately determined to be either out of scope or impractical for implementation, in some cases because they are rapidly developing and lack mature community practices.

The question of whether or how to address datasets that do not have an associated persistent identifier (PID) came up several times. We recognize that for instances when a record of the dataset exists as a designated object with a PID (generally a DOI or an accession number), the associated PID metadata may facilitate capturing some of the usage information collected in the typology; for example, the connection between the dataset and

an output, and the use of data based on the time stamp available for that connection. However, we did not restrict the typology to data objects with such identifiers. It is also important to note that the typology applies to digital data, which were the focus of the group's expertise and scoped use cases. As a consequence, the typology was designed with digital data in mind. Application to analog data (e.g., samples) might be possible; for such an implementation, we recommend reviewing and adjusting the typology to fully and precisely capture relevant properties of analog usage.

Artificial intelligence (AI) related to the use of data loomed large in our discussions. AI is clearly a significant emerging factor in multiple aspects of using data itself, as well as generating data-usage information. At this time, however, developments are too rapid and too uncertain to be included in this typology. At a minimum, input on this topic needs broader expertise beyond this Working Group.

Data in the cloud came up often and there was significant discussion of how to include it in the typology; *OAI-PMH* raised similar issues. In both cases, much of the discussion centered on whether these are access or discovery points. The multifactorial nature of broad topics like these were, in part, what led to the decision to allow the selection of multiple values for categories which touched upon these topics (*Data discovery, Point of Access*).

CARE and related principles of indigenous data sovereignty are another emerging set of recommendations and practices directly relevant to data usage. For example, the US National Science Foundation (NSF) and National Institutes of Health (NIH) offer resources for researcher engagement with tribal communities^{1,2,3}. The Working Group agrees on the importance of this topic but decided not to include any categories or values explicitly addressing indigenous data. We consider the handling of indigenous data to be primarily an issue of data generation and management, which is outside of the typology's scope. Where data usage touches upon issues of handling indigenous data, this would be in the domain of ethics, which is beyond the expertise and associated use cases of this working group. We did not, for example, include in the typology a category indicating whether data usage followed or was part of an ethics review. It is, however, conceivable to extend the typology into this direction, with involvement of relevant expertise.

1 <https://www.nsf.gov/about/tribal-engagement>

2 <https://dpcpsi.nih.gov/thro/tribal-consultations>

3 <https://www.science.org/content/article/new-nsf-rule-requires-tribal-approval-research-affecting-their-interests>

Funding use cases as well as the use of metadata itself generated a fair amount of debate. Is funding that supports research a “scholarly” use case? It was agreed that funding either the creation or the use of data is not in itself a type of data use. With regard to metadata, it was agreed that the use of metadata is in scope if and only if the metadata constitute a dataset from the perspective of the user. For example, if a meta-researcher investigates the completeness of metadata in a repository, the collection of metadata examined constitutes a dataset. However, consulting the metadata to determine whether a dataset is useful does not constitute a use of that metadata as a data usage on its own. Additionally, it was discussed whether the typology should capture versions of data. Versioning is important, but was not considered in scope of the typology, as the version is a characteristic of the dataset itself, rather than its use.

The Working Group agreed early on that the typology would focus on the description of data usage, and not on downstream potential uses others may make of the information. If the typology is adopted, it may provide information that feeds into usage metrics which inform the evaluation of data reach or impact by certain stakeholders. However, such implementations of outputs from the typology would be up to the individual stakeholders or, possibly, other overarching working groups. The typology aims to provide a contextualized outline of the ways in which the data was used, but is agnostic to the purpose of collecting this information and does not propose any metrics.

A central decision to make for the group was where to define that a specific instance of data usage has ended. The group discussed different definitions between the two possible extremes: one extreme would have been to have a new instance of data use as soon as any property changes. For example, data analysis by person A would be one use, and the publication of an article by the same person describing this analysis would be another use. While this would allow for the highest precision, it was decided that for most use cases this would produce unmanageable documentation workload for data providers and/or data users, as well as large data amounts. Also, there was no straightforward solution with regard to usage which can legitimately take place by several persons at once, as e.g. publishing an article. The other extreme would have been to structure the typology to capture all uses by all users originating from a specific instance of data access. In this case, it seemed very difficult to restrict the “instance of usage” at all, and in practice, this would create unwieldy, cascading user information that changes over time. A middle road was ultimately settled on, where the typology captures data usage for one entity interacting with the data in the User dimension, but at the same time captures all ways in which the data is used in the Application dimension, which can include several entities. This ensures that downstream outputs are captured, as e.g. an article based on a preprint, which is in turn based on a dataset. While logically, there is a sequence in which every

step could be separately documented, the group’s use cases and real-world understanding of what “data usage” constitutes led to this compromise to capture downstream outputs, which are sometimes only indirectly linked to the dataset and can be the output of other actors than the initial one.

With regard to the Application dimension, it was discussed whether within the “desired uses” of data, the typology should also capture uses on the level of the users’ cognitive processes. These could be contributions to formulating hypotheses or to decision-making, and were in the discussion subsumed under “scientific reasoning”. Such contributions did not fit well to either the *Purpose* nor the *Activity type* categories. Ultimately, it was decided not to include uses which do not result in any *Output*; reasoning does not as such lead to outputs, but is rather implicit in the processes which result in them.

On most points, the group reached a wide agreement. Still, as discussions and work progressed, some of the aforementioned issues had to be decided on, even if different views persisted. The summary above helps to trace the issues which were either important design decisions or particularly contentious. Thus, it served as a log of the decision process, as well as inspiration for future developments of the typology.

Examples of the application of the typology

The sections below include user stories per stakeholder group, adapted from the list of use cases which the Working Group collected - available as a supplementary file with this report.

Researchers

- As a researcher, I would like to see how others have used datasets I published, so that I can improve my future data collection and documentation practices.
- As a researcher, I would like to see how the datasets I produced have been used to describe their usage and impact in my activity reports, and in applications for grants, positions and promotions.

Example: A group of researchers collected a large metagenomic dataset which can be used for precision medicine, drug discovery, and understanding complex biological systems. The primary output is a publicly-available dataset, deposited in a repository. The table below describes how the creators of this dataset could use the typology to describe the use of their data by others to showcase the reach of their data contributions. In this example, the data creators can use information from their data deposit, as well as information available through research articles which report having used the data. Some information might not be available in every research article, or need to be inferred.

TYOLOGY DIMENSION & CATEGORY	VALUE	INFORMATION COLLECTED FROM
Access: Actor		
Access: Data discovery		
Access: Storage location	Data repository	Own choice of data providers
Access: Data interaction	Web download	Repository
Access: Restriction on use	CC0 license	Repository
User: Role	Consumer	Article using data
User: Permission	Viewer with download	Repository
User: Geography	United States	Article using data
User: Discipline	Biological sciences	Article using data
Application: Purpose	Research	Article using data
Application: Activity type	Model Development/Training	Article using data
Application: Time of use	Use end time: 2025	Article using data
Application: Output	Model Preprint	Article using data

Meta-researchers

- As a meta-researcher, I would like to have defined use types of data so that I can incorporate this as part of my research projects looking at data use practices.

Example: A meta-researcher is working on a study focused on the ways in which data are used by researchers in the life sciences. The meta-researcher utilizes the data-usage typology to inform the development of a questionnaire to collect information on data practices and contextual information about the use of data. Through the input of the survey respondents, the meta-researcher is able to collect information corresponding to the typology to inform their analysis. The table below shows a completed typology associated with this scenario, using a hypothetical survey respondent example.

TYOLOGY DIMENSION & CATEGORY	VALUE	INFORMATION COLLECTED FROM
Access: Actor	Human	Researcher
Access: Data discovery	Text-based publication	Researcher
Access: Storage location	Data repository	Researcher
Access: Data interaction	Web download	Researcher
Access: Restriction on use	Ethical restrictions	Researcher or could be inferred from repository
User: Role	Consumer	Researcher
User: Permission	Viewer with download	Researcher
User: Geography	Australia	Researcher
User: Discipline	Biological sciences	Study scope
Application: Purpose	Research	Study scope
Application: Activity type	Comparison or control	Researcher
Application: Time of use	Use end time: 2025	Researcher or inferred from output publication date
Application: Output	Dataset Journal Article	Researcher

Evaluators (e.g. institutional administrators, funders, editors)

- As a research performing institution, I would like to track data reuse of datasets shared by my institution's researchers, so that I can demonstrate impact, amplify stories of dataset reach and determine if there are underutilized datasets.
- As a funder, we would like to have information about the ways in which datasets from projects we funded have been used, so that we can identify datasets that are being widely used by different groups and for new research endeavours in order to measure the impact of the funded project and inform future funding decisions.

Example: A research administrator is collecting information on data use for datasets by researchers at their university. They collect information through repositories they support, indexing services, and through manual curation of outputs by the university's researchers. The university administrator maps usage information to the typology to measure the reach of the dataset. The example below relates to an instance of data use where the researchers use their own data.

TYOLOGY DIMENSION & CATEGORY	VALUE	INFORMATION COLLECTED FROM
Access: Actor	Human	Repository
Access: Data discovery		
Access: Storage location	Data repository	Default for datasets in a repository
Access: Data interaction	Web download	Repository usage tracking workflow
Access: Restriction on use	CC0 license	License offered by repository
User: Role	Creator	Administrator determined based on output
User: Permission	Administrator	Repository
User: Geography	United States	Repository
User: Discipline	Social sciences	Determined via researcher information
Application: Purpose	Research	Determined via dataset and/or output information
Application: Activity type	Statistical methods	Determined via dataset and/or output information
Application: Time of use	Use end time: 2025	Inferred from output publication date
Application: Output	Journal Article	Curation of publications by researchers at the university

Infrastructure providers

- As a repository, I would like to tag datasets with typical usage and activities in meta-data, so that users can better discover datasets aligned with their research tasks.
- As a repository or research facility provider, I would like to have information about the different ways in which users of our platforms are using our datasets, where the users come from, and capture use in “non-research” activities, so that we can inform future service improvements and to include this information in reports to our funder(s) and in future funding requests.
- As a data aggregator, I would like to measure and report impact more accurately and make meaningful comparisons. I would like to be able to tell if the data being used is generated as part of the same work and by the same authors, or if they used data produced by someone else.
- As a journal publisher we would collect/capture data usage type to ensure it can be included in the article’s metadata to enhance the citation to the data.

Example: A repository manager wishes to understand the ways in which researchers interact with the data products hosted at the repository, so that they can inform future service improvements and maximize the utility of the hosted data. The repository manager reviews the information the repository collects via metadata and usage workflows, and maps it to the typology to get insights into the uses of the data.

TYOLOGY DIMENSION & CATEGORY	VALUE	INFORMATION COLLECTED FROM
Access: Actor	Human	Repository usage tracking workflow
Access: Data discovery		
Access: Storage location	Data repository	Default for repository
Access: Data interaction	Web download	Repository usage tracking workflow
Access: Restriction on use	CC0 license	License offered by repository
User: Role	Consumer	Designated as consumer unless login to data record involved
User: Permission	Viewer with download	Designated based on data access setting at repository, unless login to data record involved
User: Geography	United Kingdom	Repository usage tracking workflow
User: Discipline		
Application: Purpose		
Application: Activity type		
Application: Time of use	Use start time: 01/01/2020	Timestamp for data download
Application: Output	Preprint	Relationship metadata for the dataset

Next steps: Metadata recommendations

We hope this data usage typology helps the community capture richer context about how data are used, in consistent ways that enable collection and comparison across different settings and evaluation needs. We invite [community feedback](#) on the typology and areas for refinement or further development. The Working Group will consider whether updates are needed based on this feedback.

Building on the current typology, the Working Group will pursue its second deliverable: recommendations for capturing data-use types in metadata. We are identifying which elements can be incorporated into existing metadata schemas and we will separately report the results of this effort.

Competing interests declarations

Christopher Erdmann, Françoise Genova, and Maggie Hellström are active members of the Research Data Alliance, an international organisation which builds technical and sociological bridges to enable open data sharing and reuse. Jennifer Kemp chairs the Board of the Open Access eBooks Usage Data Trust, a pilot data space that was one of the use case examples discussed by the Working Group. Iratxe Puebla is Director of Make Data Count, an initiative that promotes tools and practices to understand data usage. The other authors have no competing interests to declare.